

INNOVATIVE TRENDS AND TECHNOLOGIES IN THE STRUCTURE OF MODERN LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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In the renewed Uzbekistan, comprehensive reforms have covered all spheres of life of society and the state without exception. First of all, these reforms are aimed at ensuring the constitutional rights of a person, raising his or her status, creating favorable conditions for the comprehensive development of the younger generation. In this perspective, one of the strategic goals is the training of young specialists with high potential, modern knowledge, creative thinking, and fluent in foreign languages.

Nowadays, knowledge of foreign languages is the key to success in almost all spheres of life. Now in Uzbekistan, the demand and interest in learning them, especially English, has grown so much that people of all ages are trying to master it: from kindergarten children to senior specialists. The main reason for this is the rapid integration of Uzbekistan into all international processes, the constantly growing number of native English speakers and the richest base of scientific, educational, popular and other publications in this language. The ever-increasing demand for learning languages places great responsibility on teachers. [1].

In addition, the world around us is constantly changing, and the educational system is changing as well. Recently, we have seen how new teaching methods, information and computer technologies, which have become an integral part of creating a full-fledged pedagogical process, are entering the educational system, especially in teaching foreign languages.

Today, a foreign language is not just a part of the culture of a certain nation, but it is also a guarantee of success, a future successful career for students. Achieving a high level of proficiency in a foreign language is impossible without fundamental language training in educational institutions. It is important for a teacher to know the latest methods of teaching a foreign language, special teaching techniques and methods in order to optimally select one or another teaching method in accordance with the level of knowledge, needs, and interests of students; he or she must be a creative person.

What is the main goal of teaching foreign languages?

According to I. Passov, the main goal of teaching foreign languages is the formation of the individual as a whole, ready to carry out a dialogue of different cultures, since it is in culture that the ability to understand one's own culture and the culture of others is formed.

Teaching methods are organized ways of activity of a teacher and students, aimed at the effective development of obligations of educational and upbringing tasks. The implementation of a teaching method is carried out through the use of a number of teaching methods, various approaches and working techniques. [2].

Many researchers support that inclusion of active teaching methods in the educational process allows creating such an environment in the classroom that will enable each student to find their place, show initiative and independence, freely realize their abilities, demonstrate their creativity and activity. With the systematic use of active methods, the role of the student changes. A student becomes independent, creative, active participant in the learning process. But

the role of the teacher also changes, he becomes a consultant and mentor. This will allow radically changing the role of the teacher, making him both a knowledge carrier and a leader, at the same time and the initiator of independent creative work of the student, contributing to the independent development of criteria and methods of orientation in the student, the search for rationality in the information flow.

The rapid development of technological innovations in the field of education turns the problem of choosing technologies for the implementation of the educational process into one of the key problems of innovative management in the field of education. The main emphasis of education modernization is aimed at the need to create conditions for the most complete self-realization of the individual. One of the mechanisms motivating the teacher to professional and creative self-development is innovative training and activity. [3].

What are the aims and objectives of teaching English as a second language?

To enable students to write in English correctly and meaningfully, such as writing letters, applications, descriptions and reports of everyday events. To enable students to acquire knowledge of the elements of the English language. To enable students to develop an interest in the English language.

What method of teaching English can be considered innovative?

These are innovative forms of teaching: role-playing games, project method, ICT, critical thinking technology techniques, multidimensional didactic technology.

Innovative teaching methods are teaching methods that carry new ways of interaction "teacher - student", a certain innovation in practical activities in the process of mastering educational material.

These are innovative forms of teaching: role-playing games, project method, ICT, critical thinking technology techniques, multidimensional didactic technology. Technology that stimulates students' interests and develops a desire to learn is associated with the implementation of various types of projects.

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, modern teaching technologies include: collaborative learning, project methods (project technologies), student-centered learning, distance learning, the use of a language portfolio, computer and audiovisual technologies.

What is the main method in teaching a foreign language?

Today, the communicative method is the most popular in learning foreign languages. The main goal of this method is to teach a person to interact with other people in the language being studied, which implies all forms of communication: speech, writing, the ability to listen and understand what the interlocutor says.

The greatest interest among innovative technologies is represented by technologies that are connected with the game form of interaction between the teacher and students. In this case, educational tasks are included in the content of the game. Entertaining, theatrical, business, role-playing, computer games are used in the educational process.

Hence, the use of game technologies in lessons is a transition to a different psychological state, a different style of communication, positive emotions, a feeling of oneself in a new quality. Students take part in such lessons with pleasure. The game process allows forming the qualities of an active participant in the game process, learning to find and make decisions; developing the ability to adapt to changing conditions.

Game technologies - the principle of student activity in the learning process has been and remains one of the main ones in didactics. This concept implies such a quality of activity, which

is characterized by a high level of motivation, a conscious need to acquire knowledge and skills, effectiveness and compliance with social norms. [4].

The game form of classes is created in lessons with the help of game techniques and situations, which are a means of motivating and stimulating students to study activities. Intensive methods are understood as the optimal implementation of some progressive trends in general pedagogy and psychology, in particular, in the context of the problems of the educational role of learning processes. In essence, these are the requirements for any methodological system, but at present, it is precisely in intensive learning that such organic unity is implemented most consistently.

Which language learning method is most effective for you?

Immersion helps you learn a language quickly because you practice speaking and listening to the language on a daily basis. Immersion mimics the way we naturally learn our first language as children, making it an intuitively effective method.

The findings from the study show that the communication should be regular, every day if possible. The most effective method for learning English depends on your personal preferences and goals. However, reading, listening, and communicating with native speakers are the most effective methods for learning English that will help you improve your language skills.

Communicative teaching of foreign languages is teaching organized on the basis of tasks of a communicative nature. Students must be prepared on the basis of high-quality modern authentic teaching material for the conscious use of a foreign language in their future life and work. After all, a good knowledge of foreign languages is now and will continue to be one of the leading requirements of employers. [5].

Why is learning English important in today's world?

Learning English allows you to participate in international discussions, share your experiences, and gain new knowledge from experts around the world. This promotes professional and personal growth, and creates opportunities to implement your own ideas and projects.

English is the main language used for several meetings, programs, cultural events and other types of communication. It allows people to interact and learn about other cultures. English helps people develop respect and appreciation for other cultures. In today's globalized world, learning English can open up new opportunities for communication and networking. English is the primary language used in international business, trade, and diplomacy, making it essential for building connections with people from different cultures and backgrounds.

Compared to previous generations, the educational process that students and teachers are currently going through is quite different. Primarily, the main cause of changes in education is due to the fast development of modern technology. Because of Information and Communication technology, students are eligible to learn beyond the classroom. Nowadays, teachers and students are able to use the Internet to contact each other off university grounds. Instead of sitting face-to-face in a classroom, teachers can now educate their students anywhere, anytime.

In our view, the problems of learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan are enormous, but solvable. Having successfully overcome the above obstacles, the country will be able to achieve significant success in improving language education. This will open up truly inexhaustible opportunities for the youth of New Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847 "About approval of the Concept of development of higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan till 2030".
2. Avci F. Instructional curriculum based on cooperative learning related to the structure of matter and its properties: Learning achievement, motivation and attitude. South African Journal of Education. - 2019. - Vol. 39.
3. Akhmetshina E. I. Modern educational technologies in teaching English // Young scientist. - 2018. - No. 29. - P. 142-143.
4. Sharipova F. Review of digital technologies in the form of games for learning English. Modern trends in teaching foreign languages in the 21st century, 1(1), 96–99.2023.
5. Djalilova N., Akhmedova A. From the Experience of Applying Innovative Technologies in Teaching Speaking Skills of Medical Students at the English Language Lessons // Bulletin of Science and Practice, №4.422-427. 2020.